

USING KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPI) FOR DEVELOPING GROWTH STRATEGIES AND MANAGING COMPANY PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The article analyzes the use of key performance indicators (KPI) in strategic management and the development of growth plans for companies in a global economy. It discusses various types of KPI, including financial, operational, customer, and employee performance metrics. The study explores how the application of KPI helps assess the current state of a company, forecast future developments, and make informed management decisions. The article also examines tools and methods for analyzing KPI, such as business intelligence systems and regression analysis, which optimize business processes and enhance competitiveness. Examples of successful KPI implementation by leading global corporations are provided.

Keywords: key performance indicators (KPI), strategic planning, data analysis, financial metrics, operational metrics, customer satisfaction, performance management.

Introduction

In today's global economy, companies face the necessity of constantly monitoring and analyzing their activities to achieve sustainable growth and increase efficiency. In this context, key performance indicators (KPI) have become a crucial tool for strategic planning and business management.

The use of KPI not only allows companies to track their current business status but also to forecast future developments. In an environment of intense competition and rapidly changing market conditions, the ability to respond promptly to changes and adapt strategies is particularly relevant. KPI provide this flexibility, enabling companies to adjust actions based on objective data and forecasts. The objective of this research is to examine the role of KPI in the process of developing growth strategies and managing company performance.

Main part. Definition and classification of KPI

The measurable values that companies use to assess the success of their business operations and achieve strategic goals are called KPI. They enable managers and executives to monitor company progress live, make informed decisions, and adapt strategic and operational plans. Utilizing KPI efficiently aids businesses in recognizing strengths and weaknesses, prioritizing tasks, improving business workflows, and enhancing competitiveness in the market. Therefore, KPI serve as the basis for strategic management, allowing businesses to assess not just present outcomes but also predict future successes and potential hazards. For comprehensive management and performance evaluation, it is important to use various KPI that reflect different aspects of a company's activities (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Types of KPI [1]

Financial KPI serve as essential indicators reflecting a company's financial condition, its ability to generate profit, and its efficiency in managing assets. These indicators include profitability measures that allow for an evaluation of how effectively a company uses its capital and resources. Additionally, capital turnover ratios are analyzed to show how quickly a company's assets are converted into revenues. **Operational KPI** focus on the efficiency and quality of production processes as well as the optimization of resource usage. They help measure a company's productivity by analyzing, for example, production volumes

over a specific period or per employee. **Customer KPI** are designed to assess consumer satisfaction and loyalty, enabling the company to understand how effectively it interacts with customers and meets their needs [2]. These indicators could involve assessing customer satisfaction levels through metrics like the net promoter score, which indicates how likely customers are to recommend the company to others. The percentage of customers who stay with the company during a certain period is another crucial metric known as customer retention rate. The analysis also includes average order value and sales per customer to assess the success

of sales and marketing plans in boosting revenues and customer loyalty.

Employee performance KPI focus on assessing the role and efficiency of staff in the company's overall achievements. Employee productivity, employee engagement, and employee satisfaction levels are some indicators that can be measured by completed tasks or goals achieved within a specific time frame. Evaluating turnover and absenteeism rates helps the company determine the stability of the team and pinpoint any possible problems with motivation or working conditions. Assessing these markers assists businesses in introducing training and development initiatives, enhancing working conditions, and ultimately improving overall business effectiveness and longevity.

Such KPI enable companies to thoroughly analyze their operations and formulate strategies to reach both immediate and future objectives. Choosing and utilizing the correct KPI is essential for effectively managing and growing a company, which is dependent on the industry and business details.

The role of KPI in strategic planning

In strategic planning KPI are essential, as they provide executives and managers with objective data to evaluate performance and make informed decisions. These metrics enable the **evaluation of present company performance and the prediction of future trends**, crucial in a dynamic competitive atmosphere. By utilizing KPI, businesses are able to not only respond to changes but also forecast them, adjusting tactics to reach both short-term and long-term objectives. Key financial indicators are crucial for evaluating the present condition of a company. For instance, examining profit trends aids in identifying the most profitable products and services and pinpointing areas for cost savings. By using this data, companies can adjust budgeting, reallocate resources, and set priorities in strategic initiatives.

The implementation of KPI is also beneficial for **developing growth strategies**. For long-term planning, they help identify sustainable revenue sources and

assess which business areas should be developed. For instance, if KPI analysis reveals high profitability and low turnover in a specific segment, this could be a motivation for investing and increasing production in that area [3]. Short-term, KPI can assist in concentrating on particular objectives, like lowering operational expenses or boosting workforce efficiency, leading to enhanced financial results and bolstered competitiveness for the company.

Utilizing KPI aids in **assessing a company's competitiveness and pinpointing potential areas for growth**. For instance, KPI for customers, like levels of satisfaction and rates of retention, indicate how effectively the company's offerings meet market demands in comparison to rival brands. In the same way, operational KPI like cost of goods sold and productivity levels help the company measure its performance against industry norms or competitor benchmarks. This enables the company not only to strengthen its position but also to identify areas that require development to maintain or increase its market share.

Consequently, the effective use of KPI becomes a powerful tool for business management and planning. It allows companies to objectively assess their current state, forecast future outcomes, and develop strategic plans adapted to dynamic market conditions and company needs.

Managing company performance using KPI

The process of managing company performance involves the use of various tools and methods for data analysis, monitoring indicators, and adjusting actions. The foundation for measuring performance and efficiency at all levels of the company is built upon KPI, which provide managers with the necessary information to make informed decisions and implement strategies. To evaluate company performance and efficiency using KPI, specialized analytical tools and software are employed (table 1).

Table 1.

Tools for KPI analysis in performance and efficiency evaluation [4, 5]

The tool	Description	Application example
BI-systems	Software solutions that combine data from various sources and visualize KPI using dashboards and reports.	Real-time monitoring of financial indicators such as profitability and profit.
ERP systems	Comprehensive systems for managing company resources, including modules for tracking and analyzing production and financial KPI.	Analysis of the cost of production and labor productivity to optimize production processes.
Regression analysis	A statistical method used to predict future KPI values based on historical data and current trends.	Forecasting sales volume for the next quarter based on last year's figures and current conditions.
Correlation analysis	A method that allows you to identify the relationships between different KPI and determine which of them have the greatest impact on key indicators.	Determining the impact of marketing expenses on sales growth and assessing their interdependence.

According to the author, the use of various tools and methods for KPI analysis is an integral part of effective performance and productivity management

within a company. Applying such methods not only enables data collection and processing but also helps understand the internal and external factors influencing business processes.

Building an effective management system based on KPI begins with clearly defining the company's objectives. The goals must be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound. After that, the company develops a KPI monitoring plan, determining the frequency of measurements and assigning responsibility for tracking the indicators [6]. Monitoring of KPI is conducted through integrated information systems that automatically collect and analyze data. This method enables the timely detection of deviations from established goals and allows for prompt action to adjust activities. The KPI system should be adapted to the needs and objectives of various departments within the company. It is essential for the KPI system to be integrated and interconnected across departments, enabling not only the evaluation of individual aspects of activities but also the tracking of their mutual influence. For instance, a decline in productivity in the production department may impact the achievement of financial plans and customer satisfaction, necessitating coordinated actions and joint problem-solving.

Thus, managing company performance using KPI requires a comprehensive approach based on the use of advanced analytical tools, a clear definition of objectives, and a flexible adaptation of the KPI system to the needs of various departments. Overall, it is important to note that KPI are a tool that allows organizations to measure, evaluate, and manage various aspects of their activities. Many leading companies successfully use KPI systems to manage their business processes and improve efficiency. For example, **Google** actively uses KPI in human resource management, evaluating employee engagement, satisfaction, and productivity. These metrics enable the company not only to optimize recruitment and onboarding processes but also to maintain high employee motivation and loyalty, positively influencing overall productivity and innovation potential [7].

Amazon effectively uses KPI in supply chain and logistics management. Metrics such as order fulfillment time, return rates, and customer satisfaction levels help the company not only ensure fast delivery but also quickly adapt to changes in demand and customer needs. As a result, Amazon successfully maintains a high level of customer satisfaction and competitiveness in the global market [8].

In this way, the implementation and competent use of KPI enable companies not only to enhance operational efficiency and improve the customer experience but also to develop innovative solutions that strengthen their competitive positions in the market.

Conclusion

The use of KPI is a powerful tool for developing growth strategies and managing company performance

in today's global economy. Effective implementation of KPI contributes to the transparency and manageability of business processes, providing company management with the data needed for informed decision-making and strategy execution.

Examples of leading global corporations such as Google and Amazon demonstrate that a well-constructed KPI system not only enhances operational efficiency and improves the customer experience but also strengthens market competitiveness, supporting innovative development and strategic leadership. Therefore, KPI become a crucial element of modern management and strategic planning, ensuring sustainable development for companies and the ability to adapt to new challenges.

References

1. Riofrio M. I. P., Granizo G. G. U., Mayorga M. H., Alarcón C. H. M. Key Performance Indicators for Business Financial Perspective. *Journal of Namibian Studies: History Politics Culture*. – 2023. – V. 34. – P. 3917-3940.
2. Hristov I., Appolloni A., Chirico A. The adoption of the key performance indicators to integrate sustainability in the business strategy: A novel five-dimensional framework. *Business Strategy and the Environment*. – 2022. – V. 31. – №. 7. – P. 3216-3230.
3. Hristov I., Camilli R., Chirico A. The role of Key Performance Indicators as a performance management tool in implementing corporate strategies: A critical review of the literature. *Financial reporting: bilancio, controlli e comunicazione d'azienda*: 1, 2022. – P. 117-153.
4. Atikno W., Setiawan I., Taufik D. A. Key Performance Indicators Implementation: Literature Review and Development for Performance Measurement. *IJIEM-Indonesian Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*. – 2021. – V. 2. – №. 3. – P. 189-197.
5. Pshichenko D. Developing Methods for Assessing the Impact of Digital Innovations on the Economic Efficiency of Enterprises: Methodology for Measuring ROI of Digital Projects. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*. – 2024. – V. 10. – №. 10. – P. 244-251.
6. Tudose M. B., Rusu V. D., Avasilcai S. Performance management for growth: A framework based on EVA. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*. – 2021. – V. 14. – №. 3. – P. 102.
7. Grigoraş N. V. Key performance indicators specific to the human resources department. *Proceedings of the international scientific conference strategies xxi. Volume xviii*. – Carol I National Defence University Publishing House. – 2022. – P. 236-243.
8. Vivek V, savaliya V. V., Vidani J. E-Commerce Supply Chain Efficiency: A Case Study of Amazon E-Commerce Company. *International Journal of Business and Management Practices*. – 2024. – V. 2. – №. 2. – P. 233-262.